

Phobic Anxiety and Yoga

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ABSTRACT

A phobia is an abnormal fear of a specific object or a certain situation. It is a type of anxiety disorder which can precipitate a panic attack. People with phobias tend to avoid some situations or objects and become anxious when they anticipate having to meet them. Three main types of phobias are there, namely specific phobia, agoraphobia and social phobia. Specific phobia is the fear of any specific objects, agoraphobia is the fear of open spaces or public places and social phobia is the fear of anxiety-provoking social gatherings. The causes behind phobias are like inherited disposition, childhood experiences, conditioning etc. Mental illnesses, intense panic, stress, embarrassment, reducing of self-esteem are some of the effects of phobias. Some of the treatments are CBT, exposure therapy, systematic desensitisation, virtual reality, modeling and yoga. The holistic treatments of yoga offer an effective solution to this type of problem through physical as well as breathing and dhyana practices. Yoga treatment becomes necessary when we suffer from relentless conditions of phobia in our everyday life. Since yoga views and treats the mind, body, emotions, and energetic systems as a whole. It is possible to achieve this by practicing Asanas, Pranayamas, dhyana, and Yoganidra. The regular practice of these, balances the nervous and the endocrine systems, and the Prana or energy in the body, brings greater emotional and mental calm. The full paper discusses in details about the types, causes, and the probable treatments and solutions of phobia. Among those treatments and solutions the different yoga therapy including Asanas, Pranayamas, dhyana, and yoganidra is typically described.

Key-Words : Yoga, Phobic Anxiety, Asanas, Pranayamas, Dhyana, and Yoganidra

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INTRODUCTION

In his childhood Mahatma Gandhi entertained deep fear of ghosts. A maid servant in his house had instructed child Mohandas to utter Ramanama so that the ghost would run away. Bapu used to be afraid while returning through the lane with a tamarind tree, when he returned alone from the school. Even in the early morning when he went for the tuition he was afraid. But the Ramanama proved a panacea. Truly speaking the material or the subject, which makes us afraid, is not there at all. Looking at the fact, most of the fears are a result of mental weakness or immaturity of mental power. Fear is such a mental attitude, which creates misunderstanding due to understanding arising in our mind. There are many types of fears or phobias. When a man suffers from normal phobias, he trembles, he shakes and his lips and tongue stammer. Some people are afraid of ghosts where as some others are afraid of ailments. The greatest fear is one of social boycott, and cases are known where driven by phobia, people have committed suicide (Adhyatmananda, 2001). Phobias are a common form of anxiety disorders and distributions are heterogeneous by age and gender. An American study by the National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH) found that between 8.7 percent and 18.1 percent of Americans suffer from phobias making it the most common mental illness among women in all age groups and the second most common illness among men older than 25 (Kessler et. al., 2005). Between 4 percent and 10 percent of all children experience specific phobias during their lives, and social phobias occur in one percent to three percent of children and adolescents (Bolton et. al., 2006). According to yoga the problem of phobic anxiety is recognized as excessive concentration of mind on you limitedness. Yoga offers a solution to this type of problem through physical as well as breathing and meditation practices. It is possible to mitigate ordinary and social phobias by cultivating a little mental understanding and if one is given some sort of assurance to the heart.

PHOBIC ANXIETY

We all have things that frighten us or make us uneasy like new places, insects, animals, driving over high bridges, social situations or creaky elevators. And although we sometimes try to avoid things that make us uncomfortable, we generally manage to control our fears and carry on with daily activities. Some people, however, have very strong irrational, involuntary fear reactions that lead them to avoid common everyday places, situations, or objects even though they know logically there isn't any danger. The fear doesn't make any sense, but it seems nothing can stop it. When confronted with the feared situation, they may even have a panic attack, the spontaneous onset of intense fear that makes people feel as if they might stop breathing and pass out, are having a heart attack, or will lose control and die. People who experience these seemingly out-of-control fears have a phobia. Anxiety is a normal part of living. It's the body's way of telling us something isn't right. It keeps us from harm's way and prepares us to act quickly in the face of danger. However, for some people, anxiety is and persistent, irrational, and overwhelming. It may get in the way of day-to-day activities or even make them impossible. This may be a sign of an anxiety disorder. The term 'anxiety disorders' describes a group of conditions including generalized anxiety disorder (GAD), obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD), panic disorder, post traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), social anxiety disorder.

Phobic anxiety is also one type of anxiety which is very irrational and neglected but still persists in many of our lives. But there also exists thin difference between normal anxiety and phobia. It can be well understood by an example - Normal anxiety is when someone is worrying about taking off in an airplane during a lightning storm but phobic condition is when someone turning down a big promotion because it involves air travel. A Swedish study found that females have a higher incidence than males (26.5 percent for females and 12.4 percent for males). Among adults, 21.2 percent of women and 10.9 percent of men have a single specific phobia, while multiple phobias occur in 5.4 percent of females and 1.5 percent of males. Women are nearly four times as likely as men to have a fear of animals (12.1 percent in women and 3.3 percent in men), a higher dimorphic than with all specific or generalized phobias or social phobias. Social phobias are more common in girls than in boys, while situational phobia occurs in 17.4 percent of women and 8.5 percent of men (Fredrikson & et al., 1996). Phobic anxiety results in mental illness, limits work efficiency, intense panic, disruption of daily routines, embarrassment among closed groups or in society, stress, reduce self-esteem, trouble on the job or in school, changes in personality, family or relationship problems, depression or suicidal thoughts, frequent emotional & physical health issues, alcohol or drug abuse, compulsive or repetitive behaviors etc.

Types of Phobia

There are three broad groups of phobias:

Ordinary or Specific Phobia - A specific phobia is a marked and persistent fear of an object or situation which brings about an excessive or unreasonable fear when in the presence of, or anticipating, a specific object? The specific phobias may also include concerns with losing control, panicking, and fainting which are the direct result of an encounter with the phobia. Specific phobias are defined in relation to objects or situations whereas social phobias emphasize social fear and the evaluations that might accompany them (APA, 1994). Specific phobia may be further subdivided into five categories: animal type, natural environment type, situational type, blood-injection-injury type, and other (LeBeau & et al., 2010). Specific phobias are most prevalent in children between ages 10 and 13 (Bolton & et al., 2006). Specific phobias affect about 68% of people in the Western world and 24% of people in Asia, Africa, and Latin America in a given year (APA, 2013). Some children form a phobia for certain animals. Such children, even when they become adults, are not capable of driving away that phobia, which had entered their child, like mentality, because their adult mind does not drive out the fear that has entered their nervous system.

Agoraphobia - It is a generalized fear of leaving home or a small familiar 'safe' area, and of possible panic attacks that might follow. It may also be caused by various specific phobias such as fear of open spaces, social embarrassment (social agoraphobia), fear of contamination (fear of germs, possibly complicated by obsessive-compulsive disorder) or PTSD (post traumatic stress disorder) related to a trauma that occurred out of doors. It is when fear of a situation occurs because it is felt that escape would not be possible (APA, 2013). Agoraphobia affects about 1.7% of people (APA, 2013). Agoraphobics tend to be

introverted - they cannot bear big crowds. Public transport and vehicular traffic, as well as deep noises in the market place, are intolerable for them. Under such circumstances, they get afraid of getting caught, entangled, and entrapped, as well as getting confused. They get difficulty expressing their feelings and communicating their needs and desires - especially anger and frustration. Agoraphobia mainly affects adults. This type of fear can be observed in persons who have matured.

Social Phobia - The third type of phobia is arising out of incapacity of speaking, or acting, in public, or in community meetings. It develops in adolescence; and the person is concerned about shameful, stupid, or inept acts. Extreme feelings of shyness, and self-consciousness, build into a powerful fear. As a result, a person feels uncomfortable participating in everyday social situations. It is when the situation is feared as the person is worried about others judging them (APA, 2013).

Causes of Phobia

It is very unusual for a phobia to start after the age of 30. Most of them begin during early childhood, teenage years, or early adulthood. They can be caused by a stressful situation or experience, a frightening event, or a parent or household member who has a phobia which the child becomes progressively aware of. These usually develop when the child is aged 4-8. In some cases, it may be the result of something that happened early in life. The trigger might have been an unpleasant experience in a confined space which fostered and developed into claustrophobia over time. Many experts stress that phobias picked up from parents are learned fears - they are not genetically inherited (Nordqvist, 2016). For instance, if a mother suffers from Arachnophobia (fear of spiders) then it is much more likely for her daughter to develop the same phobia as well, simply because she was highly aware of her mother's fear throughout childhood.

The causes of social phobias are still shrouded in clouds of mystery and ambiguity. Scientists believe that the complex phobias are often caused by a combination of genetics, brain chemistry and certain life experiences. It is said that social phobias are more likely to be caused by a very stressful experience than agoraphobia. Some say that there may be an evolutionary explanation for some kinds of phobias. In ancient times for instance, staying outside in a wide and open field would increase the risk of getting caught by other dangerous predators. Therefore it's only logical that for many people, especially for young children, there is a strong instinct for staying safe at home. Furthermore, today's social phobias could have been a potential survival instinct in ancient times. Staying with a group of strangers (people from another tribe perhaps) was much more dangerous thousands of years ago than it is now.

Another highly acceptable cause for phobias may be found in the field of neuroscience. Some areas of the brain are known to store information about dangerous and even deadly events. If a similar event is confronted sometime in the future, the brain will automatically recall those old memories and make the body react as if it were a recurrence. It suggests that the anxiety response in phobias is not to the object or the event itself, but to the possibility that

some unacceptable unconscious material is about to erupt into consciousness. Phobias are, therefore, understood as a result of repression: when the repressed event or content threatens to come to consciousness, the frontal passages of the brain are stimulated - the limbic and psychic centres - and a panic attack results. While the threat begins in the mind, the body responds as if it were real. Phobias thus illustrate the interdependence of the mind, body and the unconscious forces which shape our experience (Khanna, 2017).

Conventional Treatments or Solutions of Phobia

There are various conventional and popular methods used to treat phobias. All those methods can be categorised into two main categories namely, Psychotherapy and Medication. Apart from these two methods yogic therapy can also be used as a holistic therapy to mitigate the phobic anxiety which is discussed later in this article. Psychotherapy includes many methods like Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT), Exposure Therapy, Systematic Desensitization, Progressive Relaxation Techniques, Virtual Reality, Modeling, Counter conditioning, Flooding etc. Simple or specific phobias have been quite effectively treated with behavior therapy (Marks, 1987). Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT) allows the patient to challenge dysfunctional thoughts or beliefs by being mindful of their own feelings with the aim that the patient will realize their fear is irrational. It involves exposure combined with other techniques to learn ways to view and cope with the feared object or situation differently (Hall, 1997). CBT may be conducted in a group setting. Exposure therapy works by gradually increasing the level of exposure to your fear, which allows you to gain control over your phobia. As the treatment progresses, you should begin to feel less anxious about your phobia. Another simple form of exposure treatment is that of flooding, where the person is immersed in the fear reflex until the fear itself fades away. Some phobic reactions are so strong that flooding must be done through one's imagining the phobic stimulus, rather than engaging the phobic stimulus itself (Foa and Kozak, 1986). Some patients cannot handle flooding in any form, so an alternative classical conditioning technique is used called counter-conditioning (Watson, 1924). In this form, one is trained to substitute a relaxation response for the fear response in the presence of the phobic stimulus. Relaxation is incompatible with feeling fearful or having anxiety, so it is said that the relaxation response counters the fear response. This counter-conditioning is most often used in a systematic way to very gradually introduce the feared stimulus in a step-by-step fashion known as systematic desensitization (Wolpe, 1958).

Systematic desensitization can be paired with modeling, an application suggested by social learning theorists. In modeling, the patient observes others (the models) in the presence of the phobic stimulus who is responding with relaxation rather than fear. In this way, the patient is encouraged to imitate the model(s) and thereby relieve their phobia. Combining live modeling with personal imitation is sometimes called participant modeling (Bernstein, 1997). Virtual Reality uses a virtual reality helmet being worn by the patient who then displays a phobic situation which is controlled and monitored by the therapist. The scene might be one of driving a car over a high bridge, while pulse rate is being monitored by the

therapist. When the pulse rate gets too high, the scene is either shut down or frozen in frame to allow the therapist to counter-condition relaxation to replace the fear and anxiety response (Rothbaum et. al., 1995). Sometimes medications can help to reduce the anxiety and panic symptoms you experience from thinking about or being exposed to the object or situation you fear. Medications may be used during initial treatment or for short-term use in specific, infrequently encountered situations, such as flying on an airplane, public speaking or going through an MRI procedure. Medications called benzodiazepines helps to relax by reducing the amount of anxiety you feel. Sedatives are used with caution because they can be addictive and should be avoided if you have a history of alcohol or drug dependence. These drugs block the stimulating effects of adrenaline, such as increased heart rate, elevated blood pressure, pounding heart, and shaking voice and limbs that are caused by anxiety (Gabbard, 2014).

HOLISTIC APPROACH OF YOGA AS A SOLUTION OF PHOBIC ANXIETY

Fear is a mental attitude. One has to strengthen and develop the mental power to face any fearful situation. It is possible to achieve this by practicing asanas, pranayamas, dhyana and yoganidra since yoga views and treats the mind, body, emotions and energetic systems as a whole. The regular practice of these balances the nervous and the endocrine systems and the Prana or energy in the body, bringing greater emotional and mental calm (Khanna, 2017). According to a yogic understanding, the body, mind and emotions are comprised of and sustained by prana, the subtle energy or force that creates all life. Our whole being is understood as energy vibrating at different levels of intensity. Solids such as the bones, liquids such as urine and blood, and gases such as wind and the oxygen we breathe are the more gross levels, while the more subtle levels include emotions, thoughts and the energy we experience in the body in practices such as acupuncture, healing with reiki and so on. The energy bodies are linked in and through the seven chakras, which correspond with nerve plexuses, and the nadis, currents of energy - meridians - which link the chakras and extend throughout the body (Yogamrit, 1996). Regular yoga practice helps to stay calm and relaxed in daily life and can also give the strength to face events as they come without getting restless. Yoga practice ideally includes the complete package of asanas (body postures), pranayamas (breathing techniques), dhyana (Meditation), and the ancient yoga philosophy, all of which can help phobic anxiety patients recover and face life with new positivity and strength.

In the practice of yoga, *Asanas* denotes the art of sitting still and also any posture useful for restoring and maintaining a practitioner's well-being. Additionally it contributes to improving the body's flexibility and vitality, cultivating the ability to remain in seated meditation for extended periods. The history of asanas can be traced from Vedic scripture to the modern period, throughout which they underwent successive refinements. Yoga as a discipline was detailed first by Maharishi Patanjali (600 BC) in his Yoga Sutras, the first systematized treatise on yogic theory and praxis. However, a physical culture existed prior to this, and Patanjali's achievement lies in collating all these diverse traditions.

evidence indicates that asanas have evolved in tandem with the general progress of Indian thought (idayofyoga.org, 2016). Asanas play a superior role in balancing incarnate health, endocrine system, and subtly takes apprehension of the chakras and the prana in the body. Practicing asanas helps counteract anxiety-driven depression like phobic anxiety, as it reduces stress hormones like cortisol and adrenaline. A regular routine of asanas stimulates metabolism and increases energy through much improved oxygenation. When we are in a constant state of phobic anxiety, our minds are tensed, our bodies are tensed and our sympathetic nervous system is heightened. It helps you improve your concentration levels by increasing your focus level (Yogamrit, 1996).

With our busy life schedules, we often ignore our breathing. It tends to be fast and shallow. We use only a little of our lung power while inhaling and exhaling. This shallow breathing leads to less oxygen supply and the negative emotions get stuck inside the body. Due to the lack of prana (oxygenated breath) we suffer restlessness, stress, anxiety, etc. This leads to different complications like sleep disorders, phobia, fatigue, etc. (idayofyoga.org, 2016). **Pranayama** is the control of breath. One can control the rhythms of pranic energy with pranayamas and achieve a healthy body and mind. Pranayama has been practiced in India for thousands of years with yoga masters passing this knowledge to their disciples. The ancient masters incorporated pranayamas in the various rituals, and the tradition still continues with preists practicing the yoga form at birth, marriage, death and other auspicious ceremonies. It is one of the crucial practices of Hatha Yoga, Patanjali Yoga Sutra and Tantra Yoga. The main purpose of Pranayama is to gain control over the Autonomus Nervous System and influence the mental functions through it (idayofyoga.org, 2016). Mental power develops by practice of pranayamas. This pranayama is very easy if you one can sit in Padmasana, Siddhasana, Vajrasana or Sukhasana that is with normal cross legs keeping the back and spinal column erect. However, if one cannot sit in any of the above postures, he or she can sit in a chair or can even sleep on the ground. It can be begun by deep inhalation through both the nostrils, thereafter exhale through both the nostrils slowly. The inhaling is called Purak, the holding of breath is called Kumbhak and the exhaling is known as Rechak. The breath that we hold inside is called Antarkumbhaka and the breath, which we exhale and stop it outside, is called Bahyakumbhaka. Every inhalation brings in some newness, energy, vitality alertness, joy and enthusiasm. Every exhalation makes you one with the Almighty power of the universe (Adhyatmananda, 2001). In the process, we tend to let go of our negative emotions, thus, making ourselves free from negative emotions. Pranayama creates a synergy between the self-energizing life force and individual mind-body-spirit by scientific regulation of prana. Perhaps the simplest form of pranayamas is Anuloma-Viloma or Nadi Shodhana (Alternate Nostril Breathing). Nadis are subtle nerve channels through which prana, life-force flows. In addition, Dirga Pranayama, Ujjayi and Brahmari also help reduce phobic anxiety (idayofyoga.org, 2016).

The word **Dhyana** has been derived from the Sanskrit word 'Dhi', which means to contemplate, reflect, think or be occupied in thought. According to Mahārishi Patanjali, "An incessant flow of attention on the concentrated object is called Dhyana." Dhyana has been defined by the Samkhya school of Philosophy as "Dhyanam nirvishayam manah" which can be translated as

"the liberation of mind from all disturbing and distracting emotions, thoughts and desires." Dhyana always starts with Dharana, i.e. concentration; the mind becomes steady and one-pointed through concentration and when concentration leads to the uninterrupted flow of thought towards one object it becomes Dhyana. The relation between body and mind was widely accepted by the ancient scholars. It is a well accepted fact that the regular practice of dhyana bestows remarkable changes in the physical and mental functions. The regular practice of Dhyana brings many benefits to the practitioner - some direct and some indirect. It not only helps the practitioner to control many mental problems but also helps a person to attain the highest level of spiritual experience. Negative emotions like fear, anger, depression, stress & tension, panic, phobic anxiety, reactions, worry etc are reduced and a calm state of mind is thus developed. Total personality and outlook of the aspirant changes for the better, so that he manages to face adverse situations in life in a better manner and discharge his duties more efficiently. The practice of Dhyana makes the person attain a positive personality, thoughts and acts. Dhyana also increases the concentration, memory, confidence, clarity of thoughts, and will power (idayofyoga.org, 2016).

People experiencing phobias are often at a loss to explain why they are afraid of that object or situation. They know the anxiety is 'irrational', but cannot access the original causer, which may be deeply repressed. **Yoganidra** is also one powerful practice in the long term treatment of phobias and extreme anxiety. Not only does it provide the relaxation skills which are so helpful to the phobic person, it can also be used in the processes of exposure, desensitization and flooding. Once they are familiar with the yoganidra state, the person visualizes going through the feared experience in the imagination, while remaining in the relaxed state: either beginning with the easiest situation (desensitization), or the most frightening one (flooding). Similarly, when in the actual situation, the person can use yoganidra techniques to relax and 'stay with' the fear. Yoganidra also acts as a 'tranquilizer' to balance the hypothalamus and relieve anxiety states. Most importantly, the regular practice of yoganidra gives access to the deep unconscious and subconscious forces which are the basis for the phobia and allows them to be released. In the advanced stages of yoganidra, practitioners are asked to submit voluntarily to threatening emotions while preserving a state of deep relaxation and 'witness awareness' to the whole process. A specific program of yoganidra, beginning with the basic technique and continuing into specific guided visualizations, should be constructed, with a teacher who can guide the person through this process (Yogamrit, 1996).

CONCLUSION

It is possible to remove ordinary and social phobias by cultivating a little mental understanding and if one is given some sort of assurance to the heart. Mental and emotional troubles, such as phobic anxiety is usually the result of long term tension or mental fatigue, which creates disturbances in our energy flow. Mild phobic anxiety is indistinct and bearable, while acute phobic anxiety disorder can be extremely distressing. It causes limitless worry, apprehension, nervousness and chronic fear. It can have severe impact on our daily routine

and opens the gate for multitude of stress related chronic ailments like diabetes, hypertension and heart disease. It is detectable when a person has a disturbed sleep or when he is not able to execute his functions smoothly. This disorder can have both psychological and physical symptoms. It would experience tiredness, irritability, anger, increased pulse rate, heartbeats, palpitation, perspiration, mouth becoming dry, lack of concentration and sleeping difficulties. Yoga is an effective natural treatment for acute phobic anxiety disorder and depression. Researchers have found that yoga may be superior to other forms of therapy in its positive effect on mood and anxiety. Daily practice of asanas, pranayamas or yoganidra is essential in depression and anxiety disorder treatment. Considerable evidence exists regarding the suitability of yoga in dealing with depression and phobic anxiety as natural mind body medicine. It is considered to be the natural way to overcome deep rooted phobias thus giving a feeling of improvement in persons.

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